

Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan (D5.2)

Project	HORIZON-ZEN - EU research programme beneficiary depositing solution in Zenodo.
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Table of contents

Document history	3
Introduction	4
Objective	4
Resources	4
Key assets	4
Brand and visual identity	4
Dissemination partners	4
Communication channels	5
Conferences/Events	5
Strategy and methodology	6
Target audiences	6
Campaigns	7
Dissemination	7
Limited launch	8
Activities	8
Plan	8
Communication	9
Sender	9
Messaging	10
Exploitation	10
Sustainability plan	10
Co-design activities	10
Monitoring and evaluation	11

Document history

Changes		
v1.0	2023-11-30	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Initial version
v1.1	2024-05-31	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Added information about EC and CERN as partner communication initiatives.● Added further activities to the dissemination plan.● Added further questions to clarify in the sustainability plan.● Updated dissemination plan schedule
v1.2	2024-11-29	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Updated dissemination plan schedule.

Introduction

This dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan presents the strategy and methodology for dissemination and exploitation activities in the HORIZON-ZEN project. The plan focuses on adoption of the project results through targeted dissemination activities to EU programme beneficiaries.

Objective

The primary objective of the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan is to **stimulate the uptake of project results by EU programme beneficiaries** and to foster the integration of best practices among key target groups for exploitation.

Resources

The project operates with constrained resources, approximately 1 person-month (PM), dedicated to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Therefore, it primarily depends on the integration of activities presented in this plan into pre-existing initiatives.

Key assets

Below is a summary of the essential dissemination and communication assets that HORIZON-ZEN utilizes for its dissemination activities.

Brand and visual identity

The project does not have its own branding, but instead relies on Zenodo, European Commission and CERN brands, visual identity and logos.

The EOR-community is a Zenodo-community setup and **managed by the European Commission**, and is as such clearly branded with the EU's visual identity.

The EOR-community is in particular **not** branded with any EOSC branding.

Dissemination partners

Dissemination partners	
OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE has built up a strong dissemination team and channels in particular in terms of support to EU programme beneficiaries, and is thus a key dissemination partner.
European Commission	The EC has the most direct channels to the EU programme beneficiaries and can integrate results from the project into the communication to beneficiaries. In addition, the EC project

	officers have direct contact with the project coordinators and can provide presentations to the projects and thus work as important multipliers. Last, the EC's graphics design team can help with visuals.
CERN	CERN itself has multiple communications teams, however their primary target audience is the general public and hence not aligned with the primary target audience for the project.
Early adopters	The early adopters are EU beneficiaries which each have their own dissemination plans, as well as potential institutional communications teams that can help dissemination results.
InvenioRDM partners	The 27 InvenioRDM partners are both a target audience, but can also act as dissemination partners in particular with respect to disseminating best practices and support the exploitation of the project results.

Communication channels

Following are the key communication channels by which we intend to disseminate the project results:

- Social media (primarily X, previously Twitter):
 - @ZENODO_ORG (8.5k followers)
 - @OpenAIRE_EU (17.3k followers)
 - @CERN (2.5M followers)
- Zenodo Blog including HORIZON-ZEN project page.
- Zenodo Newsletter (just started, so has limited reach)
- OpenAIRE Newsletter
- OpenAIRE Webinars
- OpenAIRE Factsheets
- EC email notification to programme beneficiaries
- EC webinar for EC project officers
- EC press releases
- CERN press releases

Conferences/Events

The following are key conferences/events where we will try to position the project results in collaboration with the existing initiatives:

- EOSC Symposium (October 2024)
- Open Science FAIR
- Open Repositories (June 2024)
- InvenioRDM Annual Workshop (March 2024)

- EU Research & Innovation Days (March 2024)

Strategy and methodology

The project has only limited efforts available (~1 PM) within the project itself for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, and thus relies heavily on integration of the described activities into existing initiatives. By harnessing the expertise of communication entities such as OpenAIRE or optimizing impact through strategic selection of a few prominent channels (e.g., leveraging the social reach of EC/CERN), we are confident that we can attain a substantial outreach without compromising the primary focus on developing the essential feature set for the EOR-Community.

Target audiences

EU research programme beneficiaries (primary audience)

The key target audience is **EU programme beneficiaries**. We categorize programme beneficiaries very broadly in two classes:

- **Existing users of Zenodo** - programme beneficiaries that already have one or more Zenodo-communities for one or more EC funded projects.
- **Potential new users of Zenodo** - programme beneficiaries without any existing Zenodo-community for their project.

Existing users

Existing users often have a project member designated by the project to manage the Zenodo-community. The person may be in charge of managing and uploading all content, or may rely on other project members to help submit content to the repository. Overall existing users may have widely varying degrees of adoption and acceptance of the usage of the community within a project.

New users

New users are programme beneficiaries which either have decided for an alternative solution or lack knowledge/information about Zenodo and the EOR-community.

Zenodo-users and Zenodo-communities

Existing users/communities of Zenodo are a very heterogeneous community from all fields of science. From a dissemination/communication angle, they can be divided into two groups requiring different messaging:

- Potential adopters of results from the project (exploitation).
- Impacted by results from the project (e.g. records they have submitted could be automatically added to the EOR-community).

The latter group needs to be kept informed and possibly consulted about actions with impact on them.

InvenioRDM partners

InvenioRDM partners have a direct vested interest in the outcomes of the project, as most of the results will be integrated into InvenioRDM. They serve as co-design partners and thus needs to be kept informed and consulted about the project. Also, InvenioRDM partners can serve as multipliers of dissemination activities.

Open Science stakeholders

We group EOSC trusted repositories, EOSC service & tools providers, institutional repositories, open source repository platforms and funders into open science stakeholders. While each group has different interests and can be reached by different dissemination channels, the messaging will be similar in that they want to be informed about the impact of the project.

Campaigns

Overall, the project's dissemination and communication activities will be primarily directed towards the primary target audience, in particular in the beginning, to focus efforts on the adoption of the project results. This will allow us to collect success stories to demonstrate the impact and usefulness of the results to secondary target audiences.

The secondary audiences will be integrated on a best-effort basis into dissemination activities, and will primarily be addressed in the latter part of the project. The documented success stories are a key asset for dissemination to these target audiences.

Dissemination

The primary goal of the initial dissemination activities is to grow the adoption by the primary target audience of the project results as fast as possible.

Phases

We've divided the dissemination activities into 5 phases aligned with the release milestones of the project which happens roughly every 3 months:

- Release 1: Branded EC-community
- Release 2: Onboarding of communities/projects
- Release 3: Subcommunities
- Release 4: Deposit and curation workflows
- Release 5: FAIR assistance

Release 1-2 focuses primarily on the launch of the new EOR-community and how projects can sign-up and how the community will evolve.

Release 3-4 focuses primarily on expanding the adoption as well as demonstrating new curation features.

Release 5 focuses on FAIR assistance for projects as well as scaling up the adoption.

Limited launch

Access to the EOR-repository will be open for all on launch, however only a limited set of early adopters (i.e. invitation-only) will have their project community integrated with the EOR-community. Programme beneficiaries can request to come on a waiting list to have their community integrated with the EOR-community. Depending on the number of requests, we'll integrate as many of the communities on the waiting list as possible between release 1 and 2.

Activities

Dissemination will happen through the channels described on key assets and through the following activities

OpenAIRE newsletter/webinars

The OpenAIRE webinar and newsletter are key dissemination channels for reaching our target group. We'll write newsletter articles as well as organize webinars in collaboration with their dissemination team.

OpenAIRE factsheets/guides

OpenAIRE has developed several factsheets about Zenodo, as well as open science training and guides for Horizon Europe. We will integrate the EOR-community into these guides on open science.

Frontpage

We'll feature and highlight the EOR-community on the Zenodo-frontpage. Similarly the EOR-community frontpage will be a key channel for updates on new product features throughout the project.

Training material and blog post

Every release will come with training material which will be published on help.zenodo.org as well as a blog post published on blog.zenodo.org

Plan

Below is an overview of planned dissemination activities throughout the project.:

Activity	Description	Schedule
Project page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project page public on zenodo.org with a description of the project 	Done
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Symposium 2023 - Exhibition booth 	Done
Visual identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarification on requirements for the visual identity - e.g. use of logo. Final proposal for name and clarification of who approves the name. 	Done
Publize newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zenodo frontpage 	Done
OpenAIRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setup quarterly calls with OpenAIRE to plan dissemination activities. 	Done
Release 1 <i>Pilot</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post, newsletter, tweet, EOR announcement, training material update Setup waiting list for projects to onboard. Webinar EU Research & Innovation Days 	Done
Release 2 <i>Pilot</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post, newsletter, tweet, EOR announcement, training material update 	Done
Release 3 <i>Production</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post, newsletter, tweet, EOR announcement, training material update 	Done
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Symposium 2024 Press release 	Done
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Webinar for EC project officers 	April 2025
Release 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post, newsletter, tweet, EOR announcement, training material update 	January 2025
Release 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blog post, newsletter, tweet, EOR announcement, training material update Webinar 	March 2025

Communication

Sender

HORIZON-ZEN has two senders of communication messages: Zenodo and the European Commission. It's important to clearly distinguish the sender of a communication message when sent. Each communication channel is usually associated with a single sender, however, the EOR-community can potentially cause confusion if it's Zenodo or the EC, hence it should be made clear in text/messaging/visual identity that the EC is the sender of messages in the EOR-community (e.g. announcements on the community frontpage).

Messaging

Target audience	Messages
EU beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trusted repository solution for EU projects at your fingertips. • Built-in compliance with EU open science policy. • Easy open and FAIR publishing solution.
EOSC trusted repositories Institutional repositories Open source repository platforms Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testbed for FAIR principles enablers in repositories. • FAIR assistance through UX design. • Compliance with Horizon Europe Grant Agreement. • Supporting the EU open science policy as part of EOSC.

Exploitation

The main exploitation impact of HORIZON-ZEN is achieved by integrating all project results into Zenodo and InvenioRDM thus ensuring all project results will be used after the project itself has finished. The main deliverable in the project related to exploitation is the long-term sustainability plan (D5.5) for the EOR-community.

Sustainability plan

The sustainability plan (D5.5) is an independent deliverable. The main questions it is going to answer is how to keep the EOR-community operational after the end of the project. In particular,

- What are the needed assets (e.g. training/operations manuals, repository manager)?
- Who is responsible for what (e.g. curation, support requests, policy questions)?
- How is the operation funded and governed?
- What does a possible roadmap for the future look like?

- What is the project exit strategy?

The sustainability was published. See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393461>.

Co-design activities

A key part of the project methodology is to co-design solutions with the involvement of key stakeholders to ensure the solution matches user needs. Co-design overall leads to a better, more high-quality product by aligning needs across a larger user base and by serving as an early validation method of project results. Co-design also serves as a measure to maximize project impact. HORIZON-ZEN co-designs with the following stakeholders:

- **EC** – the EC will use and manage the EOR-community during and after the project to provide FAIR-enabling depositing services for their programme beneficiaries.
- **Early adopters (primary end-user, programme beneficiaries)** – are EC-projects, i.e. representatives of the EC's programme beneficiaries and the primary end-users
- **Zenodo-communities (secondary end-user, exploitation)** – are distinct from early adopters and represent secondary users that potentially could exploit the project results through Zenodo (i.e. potential exploitation use cases). We will co-design with the Biodiversity Literature Repository-community as they could potentially reuse the EOR-community features developed in the project for their own Zenodo-community.
- **InvenioRDM partners** – represent research institutions potentially using the project results to deploy local repositories thus providing an institutional and discipline-specific context. We will co-design with all InvenioRDM partners through our joint bi-weekly InvenioRDM telecons and through the feedback and review of deliverables and mockups of features for HORIZON-ZEN.

Monitoring and evaluation

An analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be conducted to offer a holistic perspective on the extent of dissemination and communication executed throughout the five major project releases. This evaluation aims to measure the impact of these outreach efforts on the overall project outcomes.

As depicted in the table presented below, a suite of KPIs will delineate the extent of dissemination and communication, contrasting them with KPIs that quantify the tangible impact of these activities. Recognizing the inherent challenges in measuring impact for certain activities, we have incorporated generic impact KPIs that encapsulate the collective influence of all activities.

A snapshot of KPIs will be captured every three months, specifically gathering KPIs for each release shortly before the subsequent software release.

KPIs to measure activities	KPIs to measure impact
# Zenodo blog posts published	Total of visits Top blog post (most viewed) Average views per post Social Shares per Post
# Social media posts (X/Twitter)	Total views Total number of comments Post with most views Post with most comments
# Webinars	Total attendance Webinar with most attendance Average attendance
# Early adopters	Total amount of requests in the waiting list
# Zenodo Newsletter	Total number of viewers Newsletter with most views Average views per newsletter
# Conferences where the project was presented	
# Factsheets	
# Projects notified	Total number emails sent to of project coordinators